

Takayasu Arteritis Presenting with Renovascular Hypertension: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Takayasu arteritis (TA) is a chronic, large-vessel vasculitis which usually begins in the aorta and its major branches, and frequently occurs in young women. Renovascular hypertension due to vascular inflammation of renal arteries is one of the serious clinical manifestations. In this we report a female patient diagnosed with TA who presented with severe, treatment resistant hypertension. Imaging studies showed significant renal artery stenosis along with other large vessel involvement. In this case the diagnosis was made using clinical presentation, inflammatory markers, and imaging studies. The patient was treated with a tapering regimen of corticosteroids, immunosuppressive therapy, and antihypertensive medications which led to partial blood pressure control, and lower disease activity. This case illustrates the need for heightened differential considerations in young patients with complicated or resistant hypertension and emphasizes the value of imaging and immunosuppressive therapy for optimal disease control.

Keywords: Takayasu arteritis(TA), Pulseless disease, Renovascular hypertension, Stenosis, Aneurysm.

INTRODUCTION

Takayasu arteritis (TA) also referred to as pulseless disease, aortitis syndrome, Martorell syndrome, aortic arch syndrome, or atypical coarctation of the aorta is a chronic, non-specific granulomatous vasculitis of unknown origin.^[1] The disease was initially identified in 1908 by Japanese ophthalmologist Dr. Takayasu.^[2] It affects large vessels, including the aorta and its major branches—such as the subclavian, carotid, vertebral, renal, digestive, and iliac arteries—along with the coronary and pulmonary arteries.^[3] The inflammatory process can cause thickening of the vessel wall, fibrosis, and narrowing (stenosis), which may progress to complete arterial occlusion.^[4] Takayasu arteritis is often diagnosed late due to its rarity, gradual progression, non-specific symptoms, and lack of definitive markers. Uncontrolled disease may lead to vascular stenosis or aneurysms, causing complications like stroke, vision loss, hypertension, and heart failure. Chronic immunosuppressive therapy necessitates lifelong monitoring and poses significant clinical and economic burdens.^[5]

CASE REPORT:

A 34-year-old female, height 169 cm, weight 60 kg (BMI: 21 kg/m²), with a 14-year history of hypertension (diagnosed in 2010), presented to the hospital. She had been intermittently non-compliant with her antihypertensive medication, leading to periods of symptom improvement followed by relapse; the most recent relapse occurred two months prior this admission. She reported lower loin pain for the past 10 days and a history of fever (maximum recorded temperature: 100 °F). There was no history of shortness of breath, chest pain, palpitations, abdominal pain, or decreased urine output. At the time of presentation, she was on Telmisartan 40 mg orally once daily. The patient initially sought evaluation at a local hospital, where she was found to have elevated blood pressure. Laboratory investigations at that time revealed a serum creatinine level of 2.1 mg/dL, haemoglobin 10.3 g/dL, total leukocyte count 4,000 cells/ μ L, platelet count 257,000 cells/ μ L, serum sodium 139 mmol/L, and serum potassium 4.8 mmol/L. CUE was normal and CT KUB showed a small right kidney(4.0 x 2.4 cm), left kidney

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thickening of parenchyma at upper and mid pole regions with irregular renal outline, infrarenal descending abdominal aorta aneurysmal dilatation 3.0 x 3.3 mm with peripheral valve calcification, mild ascites and mild left pleural effusion. HIV, HBsAg and HCV were negative. Patient came to this hospital for further evaluation and management.

On arrival to the emergency department patient was conscious and oriented with vitals of elevated blood

pressure (210/110mmHg), heart rate 94 beats/min, SpO₂ 100% on room air and low-grade fever. Systemic evaluation revealed a soft, non-tender abdomen and mild diffused left side pain, left ankle tenderness and no pedal oedema. She was admitted to the ICU for further monitoring and management in view of high blood pressure, Acute Kidney Injury, Infrarenal abdominal aortic aneurysm. The table below gives laboratory investigations during her 6 days hospital stay.

TABLE 1: Laboratory Investigations

Investigations	Day-1	Day-2	Day-5
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	10.3	9.7	10.5
TLC (x10 ³ cells/mm ³)	13.37	8.77	9.09
Platelets (x10 ³ /mm ³)	304	261	301
RBS (mg/dL)	108	93	98
Urea (mg/dL)	47	47	51
Creatinine (mg/dL)	2.16	2.06	1.93
Sodium (m moles/L)	140	138	138
Potassium (m moles/L)	4.7	4.2	4.4
Bicarbonate (m moles/L)	28	19	22
Chloride (m moles/L)	102	102	102
CRP (mg/L)	26.6	24	15.7
ESR (mm/hr)	32.95	33	27

Other investigations showed TSH 6.52 µIU/ml, PT 17.8 seconds and INR of 1.36, APTT 33 seconds, total bilirubin 1.0mg/dl, SGOT 23U/L, SGPT 31 U/L, albumin 3.3g/dl, pre-albumin 23mg/dl, total protein 7.4g/dl, amylase 59U/L, serum calcium 8.9mg/dl, serum phosphorous 4.1mg/dl, serum magnesium 1.9mg/dl. Anti-nuclear Antibodies profile was reported to be negative. CT angiogram revealed an infrarenal abdominal aortic fusiform saccular aneurysm, partially thrombosed, measuring 6.3 cm in length and 3 cm in maximum width. Multiple

contrast-opacified sacs were noted within the aneurysm, along with peripheral wall calcification. A few small saccular aneurysms with irregular walls were also observed outpouching from the carotid bifurcation. Features suggestive of extensive disease along the aorta and its branches including to the carotid vessels with stenosis and fused saccular aneurysms with a possibility of Takayasu's arteritis. Patient was treated as per physician's advice. (TABLE 2).

TABLE 2: Treatment Chart

Drug	Dose	Route	Freq	Duration	Indication
Nitro glycerin Infusion	Titrated	IV	Cont.	D1-D3	HTN
Pantoprazole	40mg	IV	OD	D1-D6	APD
Clonidine	100mcg	PO	TID	D1-D6	HTN
Cilnidipine	10 mg	PO	BD	D2	HTN
Labetalol	50 mg	PO	TID	D2-D6	HTN
Nifedipine	20 mg	PO	BD	D2-D6	HTN
Vit. C + Folic acid	1 tab	PO	OD	D3-D6	Vitamin Supplement
Normal Saline	40 ml/hr	IV	On flow	D3	Hydration
Mycophenolate sodium	360 mg	PO	BD	D5-D6	Takayasu Arteritis

Atorvastatin + Aspirin	20/150 mg	PO	OD	D5-D6	Takayasu Arteritis
Prednisolone	40 mg	PO	OD	D6	Takayasu Arteritis
Vit D3	60,000IU	PO	Once a week	D6	Vitamin D Supplement
Esomeprazole	40 mg	PO	OD	D6	Dyspepsia

Due to her current medical condition, she was deemed unfit for any surgical intervention such as percutaneous transluminal angioplasty (PTA) as it poses high risk of complications like restenosis, thrombosis, and poor vessel healing associated with active inflammation. Patient was then shifted to step down unit as she was hemodynamically stable with blood pressure 110/80mmHg, heart rate 82 beats/min, temperature 98.6°F. The patient responded well to the treatment during the hospital stay and showed clinical improvement. At the time of discharge, her blood pressure was within the normal range 110/70 mmHg, and she was discharged with following medications: Tab Clonidine-100mcg-PO-TID, Tab Nifedipine - 20mg-PO-BD, Tab Labetalol-100mg-PO-BD, Tab Sodium Bicarbonate -1000mg-PO-BD, Tab Rencap (multivitamin)-1tab-PO-OD, Tab Prednisolone-40mg-PO-OD, Tab Mycophenolate Sodium-360MG-PO-BD, Tab Atorvastatin + Aspirin -20/150mg-PO-OD, Tab Vitamin D-60,000IU -PO-Once a week, K-Bind Suspension-60ml-PO-OD and Cap Esomeprazole-40mg-PO-OD. The patient was advised to monitor blood pressure twice daily using a validated upper-arm digital sphygmomanometer, given the risk of vascular stenosis and potential discrepancies in limb pressures associated with Takayasu arteritis. Regular home monitoring was emphasized to facilitate early detection of hypertensive episodes and prevent disease-related complications such as cerebrovascular or renal impairment.

DISCUSSION:

Takayasu arteritis (TA) is found worldwide, though its occurrence varies by region, with higher prevalence reported in Asian countries.^[6] The

condition predominantly affects females, but the female-to-male ratio differs across populations—for instance, it is approximately 12:1 in Turkey and 3:1 in both China and India.^[7] While TA most commonly begins between the ages of 20 and 30, later onset after age 40 is not unusual and occurs in about 9% to 32% of patients.^[8]

The cause of Takayasu arteritis (TA) remains unknown, and its exact disease mechanism is still unclear. One hypothesis proposes that a 65kDa heat-shock protein in aortic tissue, triggered by an unknown factor, stimulates Major Histocompatibility Complex Class I Chain-Related Gene A (MICA) expression on vascular cells, initiating an immune-mediated response.^[9] TA is a chronic granulomatous pan arteritis affecting large arteries, especially the aortic arch, and in one-third of cases, the entire aorta, its branches, and pulmonary arteries. Grossly, vessels show irregular thickening and intimal wrinkling. Aortic arch involvement may narrow or obstruct major branches. Histology reveals mononuclear infiltrates in the adventitia and media. Aortic root involvement may result in dilatation and regurgitation.^[10]

The clinical presentations (**TABLE 3**) of Takayasu arteritis (TA) differs based on the disease stage and the specific vascular territories affected.^[11] It progresses through three stages: the “pre pulseless” phase with constitutional symptoms, the “pulseless” phase marked by vascular inflammation and ischemia, and a rare “fibrotic” phase with chronic vascular damage. Clinical patterns differ by ethnicity, with varying arterial involvement, age at onset, and gender distribution.^[12]

TABLE 3: Clinical Manifestations of Takayasu Arteritis^[5]

Symptoms and Signs	
General Symptoms and Signs	
Constitutional symptoms	Fatigue, low-grade fever, night sweats, weight loss >2 kg
Other symptoms of active disease	Myalgia, arthralgia, arthritis, abdominal pain
Vascular involvement	Weak or missing pulses, vascular bruit, vascular tenderness
Specific Symptoms and Signs	
Carotid arteries	Dizziness, amaurosis fugax, vision loss, transient ischemic attacks, stroke
Subclavian arteries	Arm claudication, inter-arm blood pressure difference >10 mm Hg. Proximal subclavian obstruction can cause subclavian steal
Vertebral arteries	Stenosis/occlusion can cause vertigo or contribute to cerebral ischemic symptoms when multiple arch branches are obstructed
Ascending and arch of aorta	Aortic regurgitation due to aortic dilatation, aneurysm, rarely aorta stenosis
Descending aorta	Systemic hypertension, dyspnea, and heart failure due to aorta stenosis, aneurysm
Abdominal aorta	Systemic hypertension, lower limb claudication, aneurysm
Renal arteries	Systemic hypertension, renal failure
Mesenteric arteries	Postprandial abdominal pain, weight loss, sitophobia, gastrointestinal hemorrhage
Iliac and femoral arteries	Lower limb claudication or fatigue
Coronary arteries	Angina, heart failure, myocardial infarction
Pulmonary arteries	Dyspnea, cough, chest pain, pulmonary hypertension

The diagnosis of Takayasu Arteritis was made according to the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) classification criteria-1990 (TABLE 4) which included age under 40 as one of six criteria.^[13]

TABLE 4: American College of Rheumatology 1990 Classification Criteria for Takayasu Arteritis

Classification Criteria	
Age at disease onset <40 y	Development of symptoms or findings related to Takayasu arteritis at age <40 years
Claudication of extremities	Development and worsening of fatigue and discomfort in muscles of 1 or more extremities while in use, especially the upper extremities
Decreased brachial artery pulse	Decreased pulsation of 1 or both brachial arteries
Blood pressure difference >10 mm Hg	Difference of >10 mm Hg in systolic blood pressure between the arms
Bruit over subclavian arteries or aorta	Bruit audible on auscultation over 1 or both subclavian arteries or abdominal aorta
Angiograph abnormality	Arteriographic narrowing or occlusion anywhere in the aorta, its primary branches, or large arteries in the proximal upper or lower extremities, not due to arteriosclerosis, fibromuscular dysplasia, or similar causes; changes usually focal or segmenta

A patient is said to have Takayasu arteritis if at least 3 of these 6 criteria are present. In this case, patient had 3 criteria that established a diagnosis of TA.

Multiple biomarkers have been investigated to aid in the diagnosis and monitoring of Takayasu arteritis (TA), including erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR),

C-reactive protein (CRP) levels, and imaging tests such as angiography.^[14] However, these inflammatory markers are not always reliable; in some cases—particularly in patients with relapsed TA—obvious clinical signs of inflammation may be present despite CRP and ESR levels are within normal ranges.^[15] In our case, patient had elevated levels of ESR and CRP that revealed inflammation and damage to blood vessels. Vascular inflammation can be detected using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or Doppler ultrasound. Magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) and computed tomography angiography (CTA) are

considered gold-standard techniques for diagnosing Takayasu arteritis and assessing vascular damage. Notably, pan-angiography provides a comprehensive evaluation of disease extent, which is closely associated with the severity of TA.^[16] In this case, CTA was used to establish the diagnosis of TA. According to the classification of TA from the Takayasu Conference 1994 by anatomic distribution (**TABLE 5**), TA of our patient can be classified as type V revealing a combination of type IIb and type IV or vasculitis involving aortic arch and its branches with the abdominal aorta and/or renal arteries.

Table 5: Classification of TA from the Takayasu Conference 1994^[3]

Type	Vessel involvement
Type I	Branches from the aortic arch
Type II a	Ascending aorta, aortic arch and its branches
Type II b	Ascending aorta, aortic arch and its branches, thoracic descending aorta
Type III	Thoracic descending aorta, abdominal aorta, and/or renal arteries
Type IV	Abdominal aorta and/or renal arteries
Type V	Combined features of types II b and IV

Renal involvement in Takayasu's arteritis:

It occurs due to inflammation-induced stenosis, aneurysm, or occlusion of the renal arteries. Stenosis can reduce renal perfusion, leading to renovascular hypertension and decreased kidney function.^[17] Aneurysms, though sometimes asymptomatic, may rupture and cause life-threatening haemorrhage. Complete occlusion may result in renal infarction, presenting with flank pain, haematuria, and acute kidney injury.^[18] In rare cases, glomerulonephritis may occur, causing proteinuria and haematuria. Persistent ischemia may progress to chronic kidney disease or renal failure. Renal involvement varies in severity, from subclinical changes to significant dysfunction necessitating antihypertensives, immunosuppressants, or renal replacement therapy.^[19]

The management of Takayasu arteritis involves both medical and surgical strategies. Medical therapy aims to induce remission, suppress active inflammation, and prevent arterial injury in order to reduce the risk of vascular complications. The European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) recommends Prednisolone as the first-line treatment, initiated at 1mg/kg/day (maximum 60 mg/day) with gradual

tapering.^[9] To limit corticosteroid-related adverse effects, Methotrexate is frequently used as a steroid-sparing agent. The risk of disease relapse remains substantial, particularly following steroid withdrawal. Evidence from previous studies suggests that immunosuppressive agents such as Methotrexate and Azathioprine are effective in controlling disease activity, promoting remission, and preventing the progression of arterial lesions.^[20]—In this case, combination of Mycophenolate sodium 360mg-BD and Prednisolone 40mg-OD with gradual tapering and also Aspirin with Atorvastatin to prevent thrombotic complications in affected vessels were prescribed. Patient responded well to the treatment and follow-up inflammatory markers, including CRP and ESR levels improved, reflecting effective disease control and remission in Takayasu arteritis.

Challenges and Emerging Approaches in Takayasu Arteritis:

TA diagnosis is hindered by non-specific symptoms, limited sensitivity of ESR/CRP, and imaging limitations. In this case, lower loin pain and low-grade fever offered little diagnostic specificity; CTA confirmed extensive aortic and branch vessel disease but could not reliably assess inflammatory activity,

delaying surgical options. High relapse rates with steroid tapering, the need for adjunctive immunosuppressants, and long-term toxicity risks especially in young women, further complicate management.

Emerging solutions include novel biomarkers such as TIMP1, multi-cytokine panels, IL-6, S100 proteins, and pentraxin 3 for improved diagnosis and monitoring. Advanced imaging, including hybrid PET/MRI and novel PET tracers (SST₂, ⁶⁸Ga-FAPI), offers greater specificity for active vascular inflammation, potentially guiding safer and more effective intervention timing. In our patient, these tools could have enhanced early detection, refined disease activity assessment, and informed optimal treatment planning. These investigational techniques come with a significant cost.

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates a rare presentation of Takayasu arteritis in a young female presenting with renovascular hypertension. It highlights the importance of considering Takayasu arteritis in the differential diagnosis of renovascular hypertension, particularly in young patients without traditional cardiovascular risk factors. The early recognition of vascular involvement including renal artery stenosis is critically important for preventing irreversible organ damage. Cross-sectional imaging and inflammatory markers are important for diagnosis, while treating with immunosuppressive therapy and blood pressure management can positively influence prognosis. Early recognition and treatment requires multidisciplinary approach to manage the systemic inflammatory process and the vascular complications. This case illustrates the need for improved diagnostic awareness and treatment of Takayasu arteritis in patients with renovascular hypertension.

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